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Mis/Recognition of Dalits in Indian Literature: A Comparative Study of *The White Tiger* and *Bheda*

Pragyans Ranjan Sahoo

Ph. D Scholar,

Department of English,
Gangadhar Meher University,
Sambalpur, Odisha.

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Abstract:

Recognition and representation of Dalits is an indispensable discourse in the present era which has been de-emphasized in Indian academia. This essay makes a comparison between the conceptual frameworks of recognition and misrecognition by comparing *The White Tiger* by Aravind Adiga and *Bheda* by Akhila Naik- two contemporary novels which deal with Dalit or the erstwhile ‘untouchable’ character. The comparison reproduces various factors associated with Dalit everyday lives, such as, language, the conflict between self and community, representation of Dalit women, question of religion, and representation of the Dalits in discourse. This paper shows how Aravind Adiga’s *The White Tiger* misrepresents and thus misrecognizes the Dalit lives by conforming to a various common-sensical understanding about Dalit communities that a-historicizes the political identity, ‘Dalit, while misrepresenting their contextual relationship with culture, religion and languages. Such commensal portrayal of Dalits in literature results, in Charles Taylor’s language, in “non-recognition”.

Keywords: Dalit Literature, Recognition, Representation, Culture, Language, Religion.

I. Introduction

In the context of the non-recognition of the turmoil of lower caste people, Charles Taylor (25) comments, “non-recognition or misrecognition can inflict harm, can be a form of oppression, imprisoning someone in a false, distorted, or reduced mode of being”.

The prime mover of us as human beings is our need for recognition. We seek recognition from the other, from our parents, friends and rest of the society as well. If due recognition is denied to us, we develop psychological and social problems, turn inward and can

become destructive or constructive in some other way. The denial of social recognition as stated by Axel Honneth in *Disrespect: The Normative Foundations of Critical Theory*. He says, "The experience of being disrespected carries with it the danger of an injury that can bring the identity of the person as a whole to the point of collapse. This is where not only is the person lost in the world but also lost to himself. There is the collapse of identity. There are three forms of disrespect Honneth recognizes.

1. Physical Abuse- This is a form of disrespect that destroys the person's self-confidence and may lead him to a psychological death.

2. Denigration- This kind of disrespect assaults the person's moral self-respect, which results in social death.

3: Degradation- This is the devaluation of the shared ideals socially and leaves psychological scars on the individuals.

What is essential for one to understand that disrespect is historical, and uniquely subjected to individuals or communities in different cultures. In a caste society, it's the graded hierarchy between communities within four *varnas* and one *avarna*, and further between 3,000 castes and 25,000 sub-castes, produce such culturally specific disrespects and injuries. Relatively upper-caste group's subjective suppression of relatively lower-caste groups must be understood differently, yet the religiously *avarna* or the erstwhile untouchable caste communities tie in one linguistic thread i.e., 'Dalit', substantiated by one specific experience i.e., untouchability. According to Honneth individuals or communities subjected disrespect of the above forms are deprived of the three forms of social recognition, i.e., love, rights and solidarity. But how the form of social mis/non/recognition translates into literature and how historical disrespect, hurt and assertion are portrayed in Indian literature must be a subject of investigation by academicians.

This paper presents the key concepts in Axel Honneth's Theory of Recognition or Theory of the Struggle for Recognition. It includes the discussion on the three spheres of recognition, namely love, rights, and solidarity. One of the key arguments in this presentation is that the disenfranchised peoples, such as the minorities and indigenous peoples, have the right to demand the recognition of their basic rights- especially in the context of Dalits in India. The paper argues that the disenfranchised people have to lodge their demands in the form of a struggle for recognition against the powerful masses. According to Honneth, each person

deserves respect because each possesses unique qualities, and everyone is a free person capable of exercising their own freedom.

It has always been a difficult task to situate different opinions about the idea of representation and recognition, especially when it comes to the discussion on Dalit. This discussion stems from the over interference of structuralist and post-structuralist ways of apprehending the discourse on representation which advocates that the meanings are not given but created through representation. For Dalits, it again turns clearer because they claim their critical presence or recognition and representation they seek in the society, and this is more about challenging the existing over-representational dynasty.

Symbolic interactionists argue symbols carry meaning enacted by individual interactions with the community and actions and vice versa. One also socializes with symbols' meanings as they grow with the interaction with the community. Similarly, constructionism argues towards mediation of human experiences culturally, linguistically and historically. But it is also essential to highlight how languages are formed both culturally and historically with meanings. Place, persons, and individuals act and enact meanings through symbols and languages through everyday social interactions. In this case, self-identity is intrinsic as it does not just reproduce meanings in symbols but also in literal languages. My paper will look into meanings reproduced with languages which are intrinsic to the different Dalit communities in India. Dalit communities have produced languages which are specific to their contextual history and culture. It is through phenomenological inquiry one can identify such languages. Especially why I argue Dalit literatures by Dalit laurates themselves have such phenomenological inquiry which is grounded in their specific use of languages in their literatures through deep information and perceptions. This is essential to highlight such 'Dalit perspective' through analysis of their subjectivities. Through analysis of two grounding literatures, I will explore the specificity of languages in different Dalit communities in India.

Feminist psychologist Starhawk argues, "A psychology of liberation is one whose primary focus is the communities we come from and create. Our collective history is as important as our individual history" (23). To place this in Dalit context, the question of recognition must recognize the conditions those produce and maintain oppression on Dalits, and multiple ways how different Dalit communities/individuals respond to it. How resistance or escape from caste is enacted by the individuals and communities. How Dalits can respond to oppression can be in multitude; it can be in forms of organized resistance, individual

resistance or response sometimes can fit within the structure of oppression. But political activists or academicians say 'Dalit', do they merely mean a caste group or groups who were the erstwhile untouchable, or do they mean 'Dalit' as a political category developed with the political exposition and resistance to caste and in pursuit of the rightful recognition- which has come with multiple political, religious and literature movements among others. Dalit Panthers, in their political and literary works by Namdeo Dhasal, J.V. Pawar and Raja Dhale, among many others within the framework of Marxism and Ambedkarism assert Dalit to be a political category of organized resistance, not just merely an erstwhile untouchable caste/s.

To demonstrate how this particular clash between misrepresentation or non-recognition and desperate desire to be recognized is depicted in Indian literature, and to highlight the specificity of 'Dalit perspectives' through languages, we will discuss two novels from two different writers. We will compare Aravind Adiga's *The White Tiger* with 'Odisha's first true Dalit novel', *Bheda* by Akhila Naik, while the former is written by an upper caste writer and the latter is penned by a Dalit author from Kalahandi, Odisha. Despite Aravind Adiga does not belong to the Dalit community unlike Akhila Naik, but his protagonist is portrayed as a lower caste individual. In the upcoming sections, we shall compare these two novels from different perspectives related to the Dalit community and analyze how they represent the Dalit community.

II. Representation of Dalits in *The White Tiger* and *Bheda*

In order to understand the way Adiga and Naik depict the Dalit community, we have to analyze various aspects related to the Dalit community, like the use of language, the conflict between self and community, the representation of Dalit women Characters, and the treatment of apparatuses that are used to suppress the Dalit Community etc. In the following sections, these topics have been discussed in detail.

II.I. Language of *The White Tiger* and *Bheda*

Society and culture play a vital role in language acquisition. Our surroundings and environment also influence the language we use. Language symbolizes identities. When we are speaking a language, we are not just uttering some words, but we are evincing our identities. If we closely listen to Balram Halwai, the protagonist of Aravind Adiga's *The White Tiger*, the kind of diction he uses and his tonality, we can easily understand the absence of any socio-cultural influence upon his language use. He has Dalit past and a lower caste history, but his past and history don't get reflected in his articulation. He speaks like an upper caste and through

his upper caste articulation, he tries to represent a community which has a unique identity and culture. That's why Balram Halwai appears to be an imitation of a rich upper-caste character; he's not a true Dalit character. The reason why Mr Halwai fails to embody the soul of a Dalit man is simple: He is the creation of an author who has seen the lives and predicaments of the Dalits from a distance. Aravind Adiga does not speak like Dalits, or what is contextually specific to the Dalit communities in north India.

Sanjay Subramanyam critiqued the language of *The White Tiger* in the London Review of books, as he writes "What of Balram Halwai? What does he sound like? Despite the odd Namaste, daal, paan and ghat, his vocabulary is not sprinkled with North Indian vernacular terms. He doesn't engage in Rushdian wordplay. But he does use a series of expressions that simply don't add up. He describes his office as a 'hole in the wall'. He refers to 'kissing some god's arse,' an idiomatic expression that doesn't exist in any North Indian language. This is a posh English-educated trying to talk dirty without being able to pull it off. What we are dealing with is someone with no sense of the texture of Indian vernaculars, yet claiming to have produced a realistic text."

From the arguments of Mr Subrahmanyam, it is clear that the protagonist of Adiga is an imitation of the rich, who has been faintly painted as a Dalit. We seldom find any word or phrase that connects the protagonist with his Dalit background, unique cultural history, journey through violence, humiliations, hurt, and articulation of oppression and assertion. In order to give his novel a rustic emanation, Adiga hand-picks some clichéd north Indian words, like: 'paan', 'ghaat', 'chai', etc. These kinds of words don't talk anything about the Dalit cultural history in particular. The fact that Adiga does not belong to a Dalit community, and that results in a generalized assumption about the use of language by the people from North Indian Dalit communities.

On the other hand, let's analyze the language of *Bheda*. Here it is interesting to note that the original text of *Bheda* is in Odia, but the English-translated version of the novel is as real as the original. *Bheda* was translated from Odia by Prof. Raj Kumar. The translator uses an abundance of terminologies and phrases from the *Dom* community (an erstwhile untouchable/Dalit caste from Odisha), which is the centre of discussion in the novel. The language is rooted in the mundane lives of the community. One significant aspect of language which makes *Bheda* an authentic Dalit text, is the frequency in which terms like: 'Halia', 'Dalia', 'gur', and 'Tasni' etc. occur in the text. While translating the text, Mr. Raj Kumar has

shown some mastery in adopting some Sambalpuri words used by the Dom community. The translator has adopted terms related to the various dimensions of Dalit culture: their food practices, attire, mundane activities etc. A short glossary of words and phrases related to the Dom community appears at the end of the translated text, which allows the non-Odia readers to relate to the discourse of the novel while understanding the realness of the character to the regions attached to the novel.

In order to demonstrate the innocence of the Dalit characters in the novel, Akhila Naik uses language as a medium. This is where the specificity of languages within Dalit community is brought by historical, cultural and phenomenological analysis of communities and individuals. The subjectivity of a persona and a community is brushed without a mere invocation of a Dalit community. The cultural and political history of the people, and their access to education in languages, have been demonstrated through the mispronunciation of certain English words. Chemeni Aai, a minor character in the novel, mispronounces the word 'BDO' as 'Bido.' This particular mispronunciation of an English word tells us a lot about the character, her background and her struggle with language and caste. In *The White Tiger*, each and every character, regardless of socio-cultural background, speaks impeccable English, as if he or she belongs to the sophisticated upper-class, upper-caste background even while highlighting the backwardness and the vulnerabilities.

II.III. Representation of Dalit Women Characters

Aravind Adiga's portrayal of women characters in *The White Tiger* is characterized by orthodoxy; that's why the women character of this novel is flat in nature. Be it the modern, high-class Pinky or greedy, manipulative Kusum. Halwai hates his grandmother because of her greedy nature. She forces Halwai to drop out of school and work as child labour. She takes whatever he and his brother earn. This particular nature of Kusum stays forever with her until, of course, she gets butchered by the Zamindar's men.

The character of Kusum tells us nothing about a Dalit woman. It gives us a very stereotypical picture of what exactly a Dalit woman looks like. The character is under-represented, wrapped up in few cliched pictorial representations, and only exists to validate the character of Balram. We have been talking about misrepresentation since the very inception of this essay and what Adiga does with the character of Kusum is a clear misrepresentation. There are other Women characters also present in the novel, but they are not visible; they have a very obscure presence.

Let's discuss how Akhila Naik has handled his female characters in *Bheda*. In the outset of the novella, in the form of Mastrani, we encounter a character who seems like every other woman character we come across in novels like *The White Tiger*. She mimics the upper-caste culture; carries an inferiority complex. She spent her entire childhood among Brahmins; she used to dress like them, and observed her mundane activities like them. Wearing a petticoat and blouse with saree used to be considered an attire of the Brahmins, and Mastrani used to fit herself within Brahmin culture. This shows the initial scepticism of Mastrani towards her own identity. The fellow Dalit women first envied her, then they gradually started following her. After seven years of worshipping the village deities like: Thutimali, Budharaja, and Gunisundri, Mastrani doesn't get what she aspires, a son. The village Pujari asks her to worship the Mahadev, 'the god of the upper caste'. Only after two months of worshipping Mahadev, she gets a son. After this particular incident, Mastrani becomes highly sceptical towards the village deities.

When some upper caste people torch down the shop of Muna, a poor Dalit boy in Beheda village, the whole region becomes violent with bloodshed and riots. One day, while waiting for Laltu to return home, Mastrani ruminates the whole night about the past, present, and future of Dalit community. She realizes how foolish she was when she used to mimic the Brahmins and worship their gods. She proclaims with anger, "In which Shastra has it been inscribed that the Doms are forbidden to enter the temple? The Shastra must have been written by you or your forefathers" (Naik 88). At the end, Mastrani realizes that the belief that she had got Laltu through Mahadev's blessing was a lie. Through the character of Mastrani, we encounter a true Dalit woman who goes through a journey of self-transformation and at the end of the journey, she becomes a misfit in her imitation of upper-caste culture but also becomes anti-caste. Before the incident in Beheda village, Mastrani was very self-centred; she used to only worry about her family. The incident at Beheda makes her worry about the entire community. She thinks about the poor boy Muna, who's lying in the hospital bed, struggling with death. She becomes the embodiment of mother earth.

Mastrani's character represents not just a Dalit woman but the phenomenology and the consciousness. How Mastrani goes through many processes, from being religious to understanding superstition and the political process of social exclusion, to reach a point to situate herself in the political history of the Dalit communities. It represents the idea of change through the change in consciousness, which has been very intrinsic to the Dalit communities and the Dalit history in India.

II.III. Self and/or Community

Dr Ambedkar, in the context of emancipation of the Dalits, once famously said, “Be educated, be organized and be agitated”. We can certainly perceive agitation in *The White Tiger*, but Education and Organisation are missing from the discourse of the novel. The characters are highly individualistic in nature, and this particular individualism is the biggest hurdle on the way of organization. In this novel, the protagonist tells us about his childhood hero Vijay, who belongs to a family of goat herders, but through determination and hard work, he breaks the hierarchy and becomes a politician. There is not any reference in the novel to Vijay’s endeavour to help rescue his fellow Dalits from utmost poverty and caste-based oppression and empower them. The lack of rebellious tendencies makes Vijay not an anti-caste character but one who merely escaped caste. The protagonist Balram Halwai idealizes this character and he also wants to become successful as an individual. The term ‘individual’ is important here because Balram doesn’t show any serious concern towards his community.

Before ramming the bottle down to his master’s bone, Balram knew that Mr Ashok’s father would destroy his whole family, but he chooses his own personal freedom and kills his master and runs away with the money. To console himself, he says, “His family was going to do such terrible things to my family, I was just getting my revenge in advance” (Adiga 174). There is a faint indication in the novel where we get to know the massacre of a family in Laxmangarh. In this quest of self or community, self dominates the whole to such an extent that Balram doesn’t even repent what he did. Without any sense of slightest remorse, he proclaims: “I’ll never say I made a mistake that night in Delhi when I slit my master’s throat” (Adiga 193). At the end, Balram takes the identity of Mr Ashok, which suggests his intrinsic desire to become one of the upper-caste persons.

Balram Halwai is portrayed as a hyper-masculine character. *The White Tiger* is a critique of growing westernization in India. It indicates the growing industrialization, commodity fetishism and individualism. Dalits don’t get proper representation in this novel. They get lost among myriads of other topics that the author takes up.

When it comes to *Bheda*, the debate of self or community becomes less ambiguous than it was in *The White Tiger*. Here, community dominates self, and self only exists in correspondence with the community. There are some similar character traits between the protagonist of *Bheda*, Lalatendu Duria and the protagonist of *The White Tiger*, Balram Halwai. Both are rebellious in nature and belong to the same age group. Both the characters perceive

their respective environment as rightly chaotic and brutally oppressive. The socio-political climate of Laxmangarh and Beheda is not different at all. We locate the domination of feudal lords in both settings. The thing that distinguishes both these characters is a simple emotion. Laltu wants to evacuate his fellow community members from the chaos and oppression, but Balram wants to escape from the chaos by becoming one of the capitalists.

Numerous events in the novel show the dedication of Laltu toward his community. Along with his childhood friend Kartik Pota, he forms a Jungle Suraksha Committee, which protects the forest from exploitation by the Marwadis and Brahmins. Laltu and Kartik assemble an army of more than thirty members in this committee. This is a small example of the organizational skills of the protagonist for the development of the community of Dalits.

In another incident, Laltu slaps the Block Development Officer for ‘eating away the money of pensioners.’ Interestingly, the BDO who takes bribes from the Dalit pension holders belongs to a Dalit family himself, but he shows individualistic tendencies, which we observed in most of the Dalit characters of *The White Tiger*.

All the three aspects about which Ambedkar talks about: education, agitation and organization, are evident in Laltu’s character. Laltu is a journalist by profession and educated enough to know the oppressive politics of the upper caste. Balram Halwai is also not far behind Laltu in terms of awareness, but he does not metamorphose his awareness into agitation as Laltu does.

Laltu’s efforts do not bring any immediate changes to society. At the end, we find Laltu locked in jail for a crime he didn’t commit. Banabihari Tripathy charges false allegations against him by using Semi Marwadi’s help. Laltu goes to jail with his fellow Dalit members. The efforts of Laltu may not have brought sudden transformation in the society, but it certainly creates an ambience for change. People of the Dalit community feel secure in their identity.

It is essential to highlight that the characters in Adiga’s novel might expose the reality of caste but doesn’t address it or convert it to agitation or organization that can ultimately address the community. Here Adiga’s character might be an invocation of one of the erstwhile untouchable communities, but doesn’t substantiate with the political history with his the ‘Dalit’ political identity came forth; and as it neglects the political history, the characters is only subjected to upper-caste readers’ gaze and sympathy, but doesn’t move their conscience with by historically putting themselves and the communities in their struggle against caste, which Naik’s novel beautifully does.

III. The Idea of Resistance

Resistance is the most effective apparatus of Dalits against upper caste atrocities. The discourse of Dalit writing should be considered the discourse of resistance. It is essential to analyse, within the texts, how the idea of resistance is represented.

Aravind Adiga's novel portrays resistance from an individualistic point of view. It depicts the picaresque journey of a man living in a globalized world who wants to become rich and successful. Mr Halwai is highly sceptical of the collective power of a community. The imagery of the rooster coop that Balram frequently uses in the novel masterfully describes the condition of the poor and downtrodden. On the one hand, Balram is concerned about the conformist and submissive nature of Indian lower-caste people, but he doesn't convert his concern into praxis. We don't find any hint of mass resistance in the novel. The only time he shows resistance is when he kills his master and runs away with his money. This incident reflects extreme individualistic tendencies in his character.

Balram can go to any extent to fulfil his desires. To become the number one driver in Mr. Ahok's household, he adopts devious methods and exposes the true identity of Ram Prasad, a Muslim in the guise of a Hindu. Balram lacks the compassion that is evident in the protagonist of *Bheda*. Lalatendu exacerbates his own life and job to bring justice to his community. Compassion is the first step to resistance Balram is indifferent to his community; that's why the oppression faced by his family and fellow community members doesn't bother him.

Akhila Naik beautifully summarises Laltu's personality by saying, "Laltu was not like other boys who would leave someone in danger and escape! If he saw an injustice or heard somebody in danger, he was unable to sit still. He jumped straight into the action, never considering the dangers" (Naik 71).

Jharana Rani Dhangadamajhi, in her understanding of the thought and philosophy behind the writings, speeches and principles of Dr BR Ambedkar, says that the core philosophy of Ambedkarism does not just shade light on the issues Dalits, but also calls for their assertion, protests and their incessant struggle to be recognised. According to her it also affirms to the principle of humanism in which the farming of human mind is essential for the emancipation of human beings. She argues that the emancipation comes from the human mind questioning and baffling the seemingly normal ideas and established notion of truth. It needs to be organized to challenge oppression. This is very much political in nature in which human minds frame an ideology to raise a movement against the prejudices that disrupts the harmony of the

society. She says the text *Bheda*, through its greatly memorable characters (Dinamastre, Masterani, and Laltu), has loyally portrayed the nuances of Dalit lived as well as living experiences and the phases of Ambedkarite Dalit consciousness and emancipation. This also reveals the praxis of Ambedkarism by exposing the shallow understanding of Ambedkar and Ambedkarite consciousnesses and their aftermath atrocities against the Ambedkarites through the portrayal of such characters like Banbihari Tripathy (Baya, the mad lawyer), Semis Seth, and Santosh Panda.

III.I. Resistance to Religious Discrimination

In his *Annihilation of Caste*, Dr Ambedkar famously says, “Once you clear the minds of the people of this misconception and enable them to realize that what they are told is religion is not religion, but that it is really law, you will be in a position to urge its amendment or abolition.” The essence of Ambedkar’s argument is very straightforward. Ambedkar refers to religion as a construct. Religion itself is not responsible for religious discrimination. Religion is not something which is self-originated. *The White Tiger* is guilty of treating religion as self-originated. It mocks the Hindu gods and goddesses but ignores the upper caste, who made those gods and goddesses.

On the other hand, *Bheda* views religion as a law created by the upper caste. This particular novel treats Dalits as a distinctive group who has their unique past and history. At the end, Laltu even ends up saying that Dalits are not Hindus. We can observe multiple times in the novel the politics of the upper caste to subordinate the Dalits by using Shastras. When the ‘Gauntia’ of Beheda village prohibits Kurpa and Deba’s mother and sister from entering the Mahadev temple, both the Dom boys confront the ‘Gauntia’. The Gauntia gives references to Vedas and Upanishads to justify his misdeed. The Dom boys tell in protest, “Tell us in which Shastra it has been written that the Doms can’t enter the Temple?” (Naik 69)

While giving a speech at the Shakha gathering in the ‘Ghiapoda’ ground Baya Tripathy, the antagonist of *Bheda*, makes a comment that exemplifies the way religion is constructed by the upper caste Brahmins. He says, “It has been mentioned in the Bhagabata Geeta that people who change their religion go to hell after death.” Baya Tripathy is a Brahmin, and he thinks that this gives him authority to modify the scriptures. Baya Tripathy is a mouthpiece of all the upper caste sanctimonious narcissists, who think of themselves as god’s own agents and contrive Hinduism to make that hierarchy stronger.

The element of resistance and protest against the upper caste is enforced by Lalatendu Duria, who functions as an organic intellectual and amalgamates all the three elements of resistance: education, agitation and organization. Laltu educates the Dalits regarding the cruel instincts of the Brahminical rule and points out various sources of superstitions. He organizes the youths of Beheda and protests against the upper caste oppression. He brings hope and enlightenment to the Dalits.

Here, where Naik's novel makes a point which is culturally significant and carries the political history of consciousness, Adiga's novel only makes a common-sensical point of how an upper-caste perceives religion in context of Dalits, which remain both a historically and culturally mute. This, again, translates into misrecognition of 'Dalits' or what makes 'Dalit'-the cultural and political history and the history of conscience through phenomenology.

IV. Conclusion

One can argue that, a series of misrepresentations that we have been talking about in the case of *The White Tiger*, is the result of Adiga not being a part of the lower caste. The act of analyzing something from the outside always culminates in distortion or misrepresentation.

Snehashish Das in his paper talks about how the fictions, poems or artworks by lower-caste communities which are delved with anti-caste critiques of the unequal social structure, are not to be reduced to be merely fictional, but to be understood as historical, or true representatives of our social history, in his analysis of Jotirao Phule's poem *Kulambini*. Das uses the concept of 'subject of recognizability' by Judith Butler to argue how lower-caste characters are considered unrecognizable as they are forced to stay in the margins of villages, states and the country, and thus in the margins of access to justice and recognition. He rightly argues how lower-caste authors and artists having lower-caste characters as primary subjects in their art and literature works challenge the caste norms that play in Indian literatures. In the context, recognition of *Bheda* as the representative of the true history of the Dalit communities portrayed in the novel is essential.

If Adiga was a part of the Dalit community and had a more serious writing style than he would have done what Akhila Naik has done with his masterpiece. Like the postcolonial critics, Adiga also overlooked the issue of the predicament of Dalits and probably considered them as a part of the 'other'. It is Akhila Naik who recognized the double victimization of the Dalits. The language of *Bheda*, its treatment of women characters, its treatment of Dalit as a community, and its depiction of resistance and protest all signify the powerful representation

of Dalit as a community. Unlike other Odia novels on caste discrimination, *Bheda* doesn't represent the Dalit community as weak or timid. It shows us the enthralling side of Dalits. We seldom find extraordinarily powerful Dalit characters like Lalatendu Duria in Odia novels, which deal with Dalit lives. *Bheda* paves the way for the construction of a discourse centred upon Dalits. These kinds of novels will help to erase the misrepresentation and non-recognition of the Dalits. Reliance on postcolonial discourse to represent the Dalits will not culminate in emancipation. Emancipation of Dalits will happen through literature, and entire literature dedicated particularly to the Dalit community will bring that transition.

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